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Smart Contracts for Distributed Databases

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ABSTRACT

The topics Blockchain and Smart Contracts have received a lot of attention in recent years due to their manifold applicational possibilities in industry and science. Apart from the several advantages, e.g. the genuine history of transactions, there are also drawbacks. This thesis aims to realize the potential of Smart Contracts on distributed databases, serving as an alternative basis to Blockchains without losing the advantages. For this purpose, the *Encrypted Transaction-History Validation and Authentication Model* (ETHVAM) is presented. ETHVAM builds on a cryptographic concept which is based on the Blockchain principles but introduces *validators* as a trusted authority to supervise the update process. Therefore, the validity of entries is guaranteed. In order to realize communication between Smart Contracts and distributed databases, in an accessible way, the *Smart Contract Application Language for Databases* (SCALD) is designed. SCALD's advantages are its independence from a specific database and the possibility to run programs in unsecured environments due to its Turing incompleteness. The basic concept of ETHVAM and SCALD is demonstrated with simple application examples in this work. Furthermore, the security of this system is evaluated and possible vulnerabilities are identified. This work addresses most of the problems of Blockchain systems, therefore it is a basis for future research in this area.

ZUSAMMENFASSUNG

Die Themen Blockchain und Smart Contracts haben in den letzten Jahren aufgrund ihrer vielfältigen Anwendungsmöglichkeiten in Industrie und Wissenschaft viel Aufmerksamkeit erregt. Neben den zahlreichen Vorteilen, wie z.B. der unverfälschbaren Historie von Transaktionen, gibt es auch Nachteile. Diese Arbeit zielt darauf ab, die Möglichkeiten von Smart Contracts auch auf verteilten Datenbanken zu realisieren, ohne die Vorteile einer Blockchain Basis zu verlieren. Zu diesem Zweck wird das *Encrypted Transaction-History Validation and Authentication Model* (ETHVAM) vorgestellt. ETHVAM baut auf einem kryptografischen Konzept auf, das auf den Blockchain-Prinzipien basiert, führt aber *Validatoren* als vertrauenswürdige Instanz zur Überwachung der Aktualisierungsprozesse ein. Damit wird die Gültigkeit aller Einträge gewährleistet. Um die Kommunikation zwischen Smart Contracts und verteilten Datenbanken auf zugängliche Weise zu realisieren wurde die *Smart Contract Application Language for Databases* (SCALD) entwickelt. Sie zeichnet sich durch ihre Unabhängigkeit von einer bestimmten Datenbank aus und Programme können wegen der Turing Unvollständigkeit von SCALD auch in ungesicherten Umgebungen ausgeführt werden. Für ETHVAM und SCALD konnte ein Machbarkeitsnachweis anhand einfacher Anwendungsbeispiele erbracht werden. Weiters wurde die Sicherheit dieses Systems untersucht und mögliche Schwachstellen identifiziert. Im Rahmen dieser Arbeit konnten die meisten Probleme von Blockchain-Systemen beseitigt werden und sie ist daher eine Grundlage für die zukünftige Forschung auf diesem Gebiet.

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1 INTRODUCTION

Smart Contracts that are built on Blockchains technologies and Blockchains itself, have become important research areas that are drawing worldwide attention in the economy and beyond. The quote “In 20 years, we’ll talk about Bitcoin like we talk about the Internet today” [1] by one of the pioneers of internet, Marc Andreessen, illustrates the importance of this topic. Bitcoin and the underlying Blockchain technology in particular are undoubtedly motors for innovation and science.

Blockchains enable value transfers in a decentralized network of mutually mistrusting participants whereby the validity and immutability of transactions are guaranteed. This is the foundation of all successful cryptocurrencies known today. Innovation is also driven by the increased attention received by the idea of Smart Contracts, as the combination with Blockchains is opening up additional applicational possibilities. Combining both technologies results in a platform where users can easily negotiate binding agreements and complex deals. Projects that turn this idea into reality have emerged and are already being tested in practice.

One of Blockchain’s most interesting features is the genuine history of all transactions, which every participant can validate at any time. Since the transaction system forms a kind of database, the industry is interested in this technology in addition to the financial sector. The database properties of a Blockchain enable, for instance, Smart Contracts which automatically trigger transactions and interact with the physical world. This is considered especially interesting for *internet of things*, as well as for securing sensitive data, e.g. patient information. Digitalization is an increasing phenomenon influencing the whole world. Therefore, this development is seen as an opportunity to simplify, secure and democratize processes.

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However, real world tests also revealed the inherent problems of this system. Despite being a groundbreaking idea, Blockchains started to become increasingly damaging to the environment due to their vast energy consumption. Furthermore, the limited scalability as well as the necessity for each client to store the complete Blockchain were also identified as issues. Last, a system that treats the code as law and has no possibility to intervene in case of fraud or error is definitely problematic.

The solutions to these problems already attempted largely remained based in Blockchain technology. This thesis, above, explores an alternative foundation for Smart Contracts by substituting the Blockchain with a distributed database. The *Encrypted Transaction History Validation and Authentication Model* (ETHVAM) designed for this purpose preserves many properties of the Blockchain, such as genuine history and Worldstate validity while addressing their problems. By introducing dedicated validators, Smart Contract updates can be executed and validated only with two nodes. In addition, ETHVAM participants only have to store the necessary information locally; everything else is provided by the distributed database, whose structure cryptographically guarantees the confidentiality of this data. To enable Smart Contract functionality in this new environment, the language SCALD was developed that aims to be easily understandable, secure and unambiguous.

This thesis is structured in five chapters beginning with this introduction. Chapter 2 deals with the ETHVAM system as substitute for a Blockchain. Also, the goals and achievements of ETHVAM are discussed and concluded with a security evaluation that covers the effects of various attacks. In chapter 3, the *Smart Contract Application Language for Databases* is introduced. In which, the various language elements and the database interaction capabilities of SCALD are elaborated. Chapter 4 presents the proof of concept which shows the possibility of a Smart Contract System on distributed databases alongside further application examples. Finally, chapter 5 summarizes the conclusions of this thesis and evaluates the current state of the development.

2 ENCRYPTED TRANSACTION-HISTORY VALIDATION AND AUTHENTICATION MODEL

This chapter presents the Encrypted Transaction-History Validation and Authentication Model, in short ETHVAM. ETHVAM is a new approach to use a distributed database between participants that are in competition to each other or have other reasons for distrust or secrecy. Therefore, it provides confidentiality and integrity of datasets through cryptography, as well as the availability of information; the three pillars of information security. The idea of ETHVAM is heavily inspired by the concept of Smart Contracts on Blockchains¹ and the observation that cooperation requires a shared source of trust. In Smart Contracts, participants can freely define which data interactions are permitted and also specify who has access under which conditions. ETHVAM explores the feasibility of a Smart Contract implementation on distributed databases.

First, existing Blockchain and Smart Contract technologies will be discussed. Although ETHVAM is inspired by these systems, it aims to overcome their disadvantages. Because security is one of the main objectives, the cryptographic primitives underlying ETHVAM are described. The following section will lay out the design goals and their implementation. Furthermore, a security evaluation will be presented. The chapter ends with a conclusion and comparison of the research results.

¹particularly the Hyperledger project [2]

2.1 PRELIMINARY WORK

Provable history for datasets is not a new research topic. In computer forensics, systems that provide a provable log of events are well known (see e.g. [3] and references therein). These systems are built to prove that every result of an investigation is valid and linked to the probed dataset. A technique called linked timestamping was first standardized in 2005. It can be used to prove that a data item existed before a specific date [4, 5].

2.1.1 BLOCKCHAIN

Blockchains act as distributed, validated, append-only databases mostly storing cryptographically secured assets to create a digital monetary system.

The historic origins of nowadays Blockchain systems are the attempts of the 1980s and 1990s to create a digital cash system [6, 7]. These systems required a trusted authority and did not include a verifiable ledger system. Since these attempts failed, they were replaced by the Blockchain system.

The term Blockchain refers to a concept someone by the pseudonym “Satoshi Nakamoto” published in 2009 [8]. The author developed the first cryptocurrency and named it *Bitcoin*. His paper describes a distributed, public ledger in combination with a proof of work consensus algorithm. Thereby, this system allows the transfer of assets over a decentralized network without needing a central source of trust. This was an important breakthrough in the development of digital monetary systems.

Figure 2.1: Outline of the Blockchain principle.

Blockchain systems in general work following these principles: They bundle a set of transactions into a block. Each block is linked to its predecessors by including a cryptographic hash of the previous block. Hence, one can verify the validity of a block by calculating the hash chain backwards until the first block of the chain, also called genesis block. This approach is similar to the hash chain technique which was originally used to authenticate users with a password over an insecure channel [9]. These concepts led to the name Blockchain. Blockchain systems additionally require a consensus algorithm to determine the node which is allowed to append the next block. It is crucial that many nodes validate a block to prevent tampering and double spending. These validating nodes are called miners and are also responsible for adding new blocks to the chain. They are usually allowed to create some amount of the cryptocurrency for themselves or collect appended transaction fees as a reward.

In case two miners create a new valid block at the same time, the Blockchain will split up which is called a fork. This is an undesired situation because somebody could spend the same coin twice, that is to say once in each branch. To prevent this, the principle of the longest chain was proposed by Satoshi Nakamoto. It asserts that the branch which has the most blocks attached to is the desired state so that all transactions on the conflicting branches are invalid. In consequence, when a transaction becomes part of a block, this does not imply that it is valid. There can always be an evolution of a longer chain not containing this specific transaction. However, the probability for a transaction to be discarded is decreasing exponentially with the number of following blocks. Thus, the system is stabilizing itself. Provided that one entity can accumulate more than 50% of the mining power of a Blockchain network, this entity can then prevent new transactions from gaining confirmations or even reverse transactions that were already completed. This is problematic because that way it can double-spend coins [10].

It is not a trivial task to create a tamper proof consensus algorithm, but one way to achieve this is the proof of work consensus. It requires all mining nodes to solve a cryptographic puzzle based on the hashcash algorithm [11], which was developed as a counter measure for denial of service attacks and spam. The consensus requires a miner to append a random number to each block so that the resulting hash has a defined number of leading 0 bits. The miner that generates a block satisfying the requirement first publishes its result so all other miners can validate it. The validated block becomes the starting point for mining the next block. This approach is controversial because it requires the miners to calculate a vast amounts of crypto-

graphic operations thus using a lot of energy and causing harm to the environment. According to the International Energy Agency² and the Cambridge Bitcoin Electricity Consumption Index³, Bitcoin alone consumed more Energy than Switzerland only in July 2019. There are other consensus algorithms that are more environment-friendly but also have their drawbacks. Some of them are, for instance, vulnerable to denial of service attacks and others require lots of communication between miners.

Not long after the concept of Blockchains was introduced, people tried to store more than just ledger data in those systems. Even Bitcoin already has the ability to store small amounts of arbitrary data in the Blockchain⁴. A Blockchain database has several decisive benefits. All data is immutable and tamper proof. The history of a dataset is verifiable. Last, the validity of the current state of the database can be proven at any time by any participant. However, storing data in a Blockchain has some serious disadvantages. To begin with, the Blockchain data is replicated between all clients and it is impossible to remove once it is uploaded. Due to that reason, a Blockchain needs tremendous amounts of storage space if used for bigger datasets. Secondly, the whole network must check each block. Therefore, the throughput is limited and even worse, on a per node level, decreasing with the number of participants. Moreover, because of the block structure, SQL-like queries are inefficient. There are already projects and research developing mitigations of these problems [2, 12] and only the future will tell if it is possible to overcome the limitations of storing data in a Blockchain. Many approaches focus on a specific use case like the Chronicle project [13], which allows the participants of the network to publish verifiable data under the assumption that no participant will act maliciously. There are also critical voices pointing out that, for most real world problems, Blockchains are possibly not the best solution [14].

²<https://www.iea.org/>

³<https://www.cbeci.org/>

⁴This is realized by putting encoded data into a transaction's note field. It caused numerous discussions and controversy because this functionality was abused to put computer viruses and child pornography into the Bitcoin Blockchain where this data cannot be removed.

2.1.2 SMART CONTRACTS

Popular use cases for the Blockchain storage are Smart Contracts. A Smart Contract is a piece of code that is executed by the nodes of a Blockchain network preserving the properties of irreversibility and validity. Smart contracts can, for instance, bind a payment to a condition. The code becomes like a law and enforces itself. These properties can be used to reproduce economic contracts like payment reduction in case of delayed delivery. Nonetheless, it is a problem of Smart Contracts that the more complex a contract becomes, the less likely a faulty or even malicious section is spotted. Additionally, because of the irreversible nature of the underlying Blockchain, it is impossible to revert damage. In June 2016, an attacker stole Ether, the cryptocurrency of the Ethereum network, worth 50 million US dollars due to a faulty Smart Contract [15]. A hard fork⁵ of the Ethereum Blockchain was necessary to revert the damage. Since that incident, the Ethereum network is split. The fundamental problem that code can have malicious side effects which are disguised from the reader and therefore very hard to spot is shown by the Underhanded C Contest⁶.

2.1.3 DISTRIBUTED DATABASES

Databases are used to provide an organized collection of data with the ability to update, search and combine datasets. Most relational databases fulfill the ACID [16] properties to guarantee validity even in case of errors, power loss, etc.

- **Atomicity** guarantees that each transaction is handled as a unit. It can either fail or succeed but never be “half-done”.
- **Consistency** ensures that every transaction results in a valid database state.
- **Isolation** warrants that a set of concurrent transactions result in the same final state as if the transactions were executed sequentially. The transactions must not interfere with each other.
- **Durability** makes certain that, once a transaction is committed, it will never be lost. A power loss, for instance, will not revert any committed transactions.

⁵A new version of the client software was released that pinned an alternative chain where the malicious transaction got replaced. Even though the majority of the network accepted the patch, a significant part of the network continued using the unaltered Blockchain and is now known as Ethereum Classic.

⁶<http://www.underhanded-c.org>

Distributed data storage systems became a research topic to overcome the bandwidth and storage limitation of single node databases as well as to prevent downtime in case of a hardware fault. A fundamental principle of distributing data access is the CAP-theorem [17, 18], whose name refers to the following properties:

- **Consistency** here connotes that every read operation on the distributed database will either return the most recent written value or fail, in contrary to the ACID definition.
- **Availability** means that every request receives a valid response.
- **Partition tolerance** describes that the system remains operational even if messages are dropped or delayed. Partition tolerance is considered the most important property because message drops and delays are inevitable.

It was proven that the realization of a system that fulfills all three properties is impossible since no distributed system can prevent a network error in which case the network will split into two or more distinct parts. In this moment, a distributed database needs to drop either consistency or availability. If consistency is dropped, the database is called eventually consistent and will remain functional in case of network errors by accepting the risk of data loss. However, if consistency must be guaranteed, the database has to wait for the network to heal before answering any requests. The idea of the CAP-theorem is extended by the PACELC-theorem declaring that even if the network remains fully operational, a distributed database has to choose between optimizing latency and preserving consistency [19].

2.2 CRYPTOGRAPHY

As the cryptographic primitives, symmetric and asymmetric encryption, timestamps, key derivation and hash functions were used for the realization of ETHVAM. They will be elaborated in the following sections.

2.2.1 SYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION

Symmetric encryption is implemented using the Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) [20] in the Synthetic Initialization Vector (SIV) [21] block cipher mode of operation. This combination provides authenticated and nonce misuse-resistant encryption. The downside of AES-SIV is a performance reduction because the plaintext needs to be processed twice to achieve the nonce misuse resistance. For ETHVAM however, this performance penalty is negligible because the overall computing time for AES-SIV is small in comparison to the other calculations that contribute to ETHVAMs functionality.

2.2.2 KEY DERIVATION FUNCTION

The “script” key derivation function [22] is used to derive a cryptographic keys from passphrases and to generate padding data. A key derivation function takes as input a passphrase and a salt; that is to say, a non secret, random value that is used by a key derivation function to prevent the generation of same keys for same passphrases. It then generates arbitrary amounts of pseudo-random data which can be used for cryptographic operations as well as to authenticate users. Script is designed to prevent brute-force attacks by increasing the computational costs alongside the memory requirements. Since the amount of memory that can be placed next to a computational unit is limited and the access of distant memory is time consuming, script disables attacks with specialized hardware. These properties also qualify script as a deterministic random number generator for padding data because it prevents brute-forcing seeds in order to control parts of the padding data.

The performance of script can be adjusted by three parameters. The parameter N controls the CPU and memory cost, the parameter r finetunes the size of sequential memory reads and the parameter p manages parallelization. The author of script

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recommends [23] $N = 2^{20}$, $r = 8$, $p = 1$ for file encryption which takes about 3.1 seconds on a 3.20GHz Intel Core i7-8700 CPU. When scrypt is used as deterministic random number generator, the parameters are adjusted for higher performance; e.g. with the parameters $N = 2^{10}$, $r = 8$, $p = 1$, one run of scrypt takes only 4.6 milliseconds on the mentioned processor.

2.2.3 TIMESTAMPS

Timestamps are used in various parts of ETHVAM and are an important part of the security model. To prevent confusion due to different time zones, all timestamps use the Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) as reference. UTC timestamps are standardized in the ISO 18014-3 standard [5] as well as in RFC 3339 [24]. These standards define an unambiguous, human-readable notation for timestamps. Unfortunately, many implementations deviate from the standard, which in turn has led to many libraries interpreting timestamps laxly. This can cause security vulnerabilities and therefore each timestamp is checked for strict standard compliance before use. Malformed timestamps are rejected with an appropriate error message.

2.2.4 ASYMMETRIC ENCRYPTION

Asymmetric (public-private key) encryption in ETHVAM originates from the NaCl [25] library of Daniel J. Bernstein, Tanja Lange and Peter Schwabe. NaCl is well known for its easy usage and aims to “avoid various types of cryptographic disasters suffered by previous cryptographic libraries” [26]. It uses elliptic curve cryptography based on the Montgomery curve [27]: Curve25519 [28, 29]. ETHVAM uses the portable libsodium [30] implementation of NaCl in Python through the libnacl [31] wrapper library. NaCl also supplies cryptographic signatures which require a separate sign-verify key pair.

Key objects in ETHVAM were designed to enclose two NaCl keys, one for encryption and one for signatures. An additional name tag helps human users to identify the entity a key belongs to but is otherwise optional. Furthermore, ETHVAM public keys are employed not only to encrypt data and validate signatures, but they also act as identifiers. For this purpose, a concatenation of the encryption key and the verification key is used. This links an identity directly to the key material and is therefore unambiguous.

Figure 2.2: Visualization of the ETHVAM key object layout.

The ETHVAM public key object also contains a list of certifications which allows users to transfer their permissions to other identities. A public key can have any number of certifications attached. A certification consists of an identifier of the signer, an expiry date and a signature. The identifier of the signer is used to verify the certification and to determine which user has signed the key. The expiry date restricts the period in which a certification is valid. The signature is calculated on the concatenation of the signed key’s identifier and the expiry date. Hence, any change to the expiry date invalidates the certificate.

Figure 2.2 shows that an ETHVAM private key includes the corresponding public key object. This design simplifies the usage and management of the keys.

2.2.5 HASH FUNCTION

BLAKE2b [32] is used as cryptographic hash function and message authentication code. It provides security guarantees similar to the Secure Hash Algorithm 3 (SHA-3), but is faster on 64-bit architectures [33]. It was chosen because NaCl already uses it. Moreover, introducing SHA-3 would come with performance penalties and unnecessary increase in the complexity of ETHVAM.

2.3 GOALS AND REALIZATION

The main goal in the design of ETHVAM is to provide functionality comparable to Smart Contracts and verifiable history on a distributed database while keeping as many advantages of Blockchain storages as possible and minimizing the disadvantages like energy consumption as well as limited scalability and throughput. The unique property of Blockchain that makes the collaboration of mutual mistrusting entities possible, creates most of the mentioned disadvantages. However, it is not necessarily needed in many use cases because most of the time some controlling instances are present. For example in business settings, there are laws or health regulation agencies that limit and supervise processes.

Therefore, ETHVAM introduces a controlling instance into the system which reduces the workload and resource consumption of its participants. In ETHVAM, the mining process becomes obsolete because validators are responsible for supervising and accepting changes to the Worldstate. Furthermore, an append-only database, which holds all the data the clients work with, replaces the Blockchain as storage system. A distributed database improves the throughput and allows vast amounts of data to be stored. Theoretically, it can scale almost infinitely.

Figure 2.3: Outline of an ETHVAM dataset update.

Under these circumstances, the update process works a lot differently than in Blockchain systems. If a client makes changes to an entry of the database, they need to be approved by the validator before they are accepted. In order to do that, another distributed database is needed to store the proposed updates. Finally, the validator fetches the proposals out of the temporary storage, validates them and updates the Worldstate if they are in accordance to the requirements of the contract. A draft of the update process is visualized in figure 2.3

To realize a data management system as described, several more precise goals were defined. This section lists the desired properties of ETHVAM and explains how they were implemented.

- **Secrecy**
Only the accessors and the relevant validators can read an entry.
- **Genuine history**
The history of each dataset is verifiable to the point of its first appearance.
- **Verifiability**
Any unauthorized change to a dataset can be detected. Accordingly, it can be proven that the current state was created by a valid, authorized update.
- **Plasticity**
Any process that requires data exchange can be modeled.
- **Change control**
The ability to change an entry is subject to predefined restrictions.
- **Accountability**
Any valid change can be backtracked to its author.
- **Viability**
There is no single point of failure. If one node is failing, the system still remains operative and repairs itself.
- **Scalability**
Any number of nodes, clients and validators can be added so that the system can grow on demand.
- **Validity of entries**
Only valid entries are stored in the Worldstate database.

2.3.1 DATABASE CHOICE, MANAGEMENT AND ENTRY LAYOUT

Most importantly, the databases for the Worldstate and the proposals have to ensure the *viability* and *scalability*. In addition, other features were taken into consideration for selecting a feasible database system, as will be discussed in the following.

The database must provide strong consistency because no data loss can be tolerated in order to fulfill the validity of entries. Thus, no eventually consistent system can be used. A system that grows on demand needs the ability to redistribute the data and therefore “heal” itself when single nodes are taken offline for any reason. In such an event, the lost data must be resupplied by other nodes and redundancy has to be restored automatically to fulfill the goal of *viability*. This is also advantageous when hardware is replaced because this property allows to add an empty node to the database and the system will rebalance itself. The viability goal also implicates that the data must be stored on different geographical locations to prevent failures due to disasters that could make a datacenter unavailable. In consequence, the database has to be synchronized using the internet. This is also beneficial because data can be stored nearby the users so the latency of requests can be reduced. From a security point of view, an open source licensing model is favorable because it allows researchers to find bugs and misconceptions, hence improving the system’s overall security. Another common source of errors is the install and setup process. The more complex this process becomes, the more error-prone and vulnerable to misconfiguration it gets. This makes a simple install process with few dependencies preferable. An easy installation is also advantageous when different systems are supposed to be integrated into the database network. Last, the well known and understood relational database concept is beneficial when the database interactions use the Simple Query Language (SQL) [34]. Most software and programming languages already have bindings to SQL because it is the widely used standard approach to interact with relational databases.

Relational distributed data management systems that meet most these requirements are quite new on the market and are sometimes referred to with the term NewSQL databases. During the selection process, most of the available products were sorted out because they do not fulfill the desired criteria. In the end, yugabyteDB⁷ and cockroachDB⁸ were considered and since cockroachDB is much further developed it

⁷<https://docs.yugabyte.com>

⁸<https://www.cockroachlabs.com/docs/stable/>

became the basis for ETHVAM. CockroachDB also supports the PostgreSQL wire protocol so it is compatible with client software for one of the most advanced relational databases [35].

The distributed database management is a crucial part of ETHVAM's security. Therefore, administrative privileges must be used carefully and database nodes should be localized in a secured environment and administrated with special diligence. CockroachDB secures its connections with TLS 1.2 [36] and requires the setup of a certification authority (CA) for the cluster. A CA is responsible for the approval of database nodes, validators and clients. Hence, it is the root of database security. Naturally, the entity in control of the CA is also the database administrator and manages the basic database permissions like ensuring that the Worldstate is append-only, that only validators can delete proposals and so on. The CA needs to examine the security measures and trustworthiness of a potential node administrator before accepting the new computer to become a part of the CockroachDB network. This is the most critical task of the CA because even one compromised CockroachDB node can lead to the loss of control over the whole database. Regular offside backups of the Worldstate and proposal database can help to recover from such a disaster, but the overall viability cannot be ensured in the case of a malicious attacker gaining control over CockroachDB nodes. When the database is administrated correctly, client certificates are less critical to the system's overall security and the survey can be done by administrators of a security context. Malicious clients can only harm the security context they participate in. Therefore, the administrator of the context is responsible and should vouch for the clients in their responsibility. On behalf of a security context recommendation, the CA can accept new clients. In case of an incident, the CA can roll-out new certificates and restore the cluster's security. Although ETHVAM only stores encrypted entries in the database, the administration of the authorization concept makes the certification authority one of the most important parts of ETHVAM's security model.

After discussing the security of the outermost layer, the structure and security measures of the entries will be explained in the following. The Worldstate database's layout is inspired by the way Blockchains secure their history. Each dataset is represented by a distinct table of the Worldstate database. A table stores the successive versions of a dataset identified by their revision number as primary key. This, in combination with the Worldstate database being append-only, relates to the genuine history goal. Therefore, the last row holds the most recent version of a dataset and the table name

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references the dataset itself. To achieve secrecy, the entry’s data is encrypted with AES-SIV. Prior to encrypting, the data is padded to the next 10kB block to prevent the leakage of information due to the size of an entry. The corresponding key is secured by secret key cryptography to restrict access. For each accessor, the AES-key is encrypted with the accessor’s public key and stored next to the data in a keyslot. Since the author of an entry is not necessarily known to the accessing client, the keyslots are not signed by the author. To obfuscate the number of accessors, the keyslots are padded to a multiple of 10 by adding random data. Similar to a Blockchain, each entry references its predecessor by including a BLAKE2b hash of the previous entry. Each entry is also signed by at least the author and one responsible validator to ensure verifiability. The signatures include the revision number, the encrypted data, the keyslots and the predecessor’s hash which completes and secures the whole entry. As a result, rows in the tables of the Worldstate database have the following structure:

revision	encrypted data	keyslots	parent’s hash	signatures
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The presented Worldstate database layout provides access control through encryption, but to provide Smart Contract functionality further logic is needed. The encrypted data section of a Worldstate entry needs to contain all information relevant for a Smart Contract. The unencrypted data is serialized in the JSON [37] format. Thus, it can easily be padded using whitespaces and is also easy to debug because it is human-readable. Furthermore, the JSON format specification does not allow any active content and can be considered simple enough to be safe. [38] The serialized data is composed of seven main elements. Most importantly, the entry consists of the **data** elements regarding the Smart Contract and the **code** of the Smart Contract defining which operations can be performed on the data. This realizes the goal of plasticity. In addition, it comprises the **access control lists (ACL)** restricting, on the one hand, which code can be executed by whom and, on the other hand, who is allowed to change which data element. It also contains the function and its parameters that created this dataset which are referenced by the label **history**. In combination with the also stored public key of the **author**, this allows a validating entity to recreate the current dataset guaranteeing the genuine history. The **author** field additionally allows to verify the signature of the encrypted entry, thus providing accountability. Finally, a **timestamp** and a list of **accessors** that are allowed to read it are part of each dataset.

code	data	history	author	timestamp	ACL	accessors
------	------	---------	--------	-----------	-----	-----------

To enable the validators to directly fetch the update proposals in their responsibility, the proposals are stored in database tables named with the public key of the used client.⁹ The validity of each Worldstate entry is guaranteed because each entry has to be checked by a responsible validator. An entry in one of the proposal tables consists of a counter which is used as primary key for the table followed by AES-SIV encrypted data and keyslots similar to the Worldstate entries. The keyslots belong to the relevant validators of the dataset and are stretched to a multiple of 5. In contrary to the Worldstate keyslots, each keyslot is not only encrypted but also signed by the creator. This layout of the table, in combination with the AES-SIV encryption scheme ensures the verifiability and accountability as well as the secrecy of update proposals. The last column in the table is reserved for the validators and holds information about the processing status of a proposal. This field contains integer values initialized with 0. A draft of an entry looks like this:

counter	encrypted data	keyslots	processing state
---------	----------------	----------	------------------

The contents of the encrypted data include the proposed Worldstate entry in a JSON representation and the ephemeral private key that is used to sign the keyslots. This key is needed by the validators to recreate the keyslots in the verification process. The knowledge about this key is not critical for the security of ETHVAM because it is unique per entry and the keyslots are signed by the creator. Therefore, a malicious validator would be detected if it adds additional keys to the keyslots.

2.3.2 SECURITY CONTEXT AND VALIDATORS

To enable different stakeholders to use the same database, ETHVAM supports different security contexts (SC). A SC allows exclusive interactions between participants via their client software. Associated Worldstate entries are inaccessible for other clients due to encryption. A SC is defined by a list of clients identified by their ETHVAM public keys and a list of validators responsible for the SC.¹⁰ Each validator needs the public key information of all clients in its responsibility and each client needs the public keys of its superior validators. The administrator of the SC is responsible for verifying the participating clients and recommends them to the CA which will grant

⁹Participants can propose changes under different keys because they may participate in various security contexts.

¹⁰Although it is possible to have multiple validators per security context, this first study only considers security contexts with one responsible validator.

them access to the Worldstate and the proposals database. Additionally, they have to manage the entry creation rights of the clients is their responsibility.

A SC administrator acts as a local source of trust and has to be approved by the CA. The validators of a SC review all changes to the Worldstate database that are proposed by the SC's clients. Therefore, all associated participants have to trust the SC administrator.

To provide and update the necessary information for the validators, a distinct Worldstate database table for each security context is used. This table is organized like the above mentioned tables. However, unlike these tables, it should only be readable to the SC administrator's clients and the validators. The entries contain the latest client list and contact information which is used to inform the clients' administrator if a proposal fails to become Worldstate. Moreover, this table holds information on a client's permission to create new entries or whether it can only work with already existing ones. The associated validators will periodically fetch this dataset and update their behavior according to it.

Validators are created with the corresponding SC and should not be changed. Hence, the key material and number of validators in a SC can be considered stable, which requires the SC administrator to apply strong security measures to the validators. Furthermore, it is considered feasible to inform the participants of the SC in case of validator changes whereby clients have to update their key list.

With further research, it should be possible to extend ETHVAM's capabilities to provide interactions between different SCs. This would require the validators of the involved SCs to work together in order to verify such an entry.

2.3.3 CLIENT CREATION

An ETHVAM client is a software built to interact with other clients using the Worldstate database by reading data and proposing changes. Each client is part of a SC and can only interact with other clients of the same SC. To become operational, the human participant generates an ETHVAM private key as well as a TLS certificate and sends the public parts of them to the desired SC administrator in order to request admittance. When the request is accepted, the client's TLS certificate is eventually signed by the CA and the SC administrator adds the client's public key to the validator's list.

Additionally, the client is provided with the public keys of the responsible validators. The SC administrator is also in charge of granting the client the permission to create new database entries. Now, the client can interact with other clients of the same SC if they are willing to and update the respective entries. In case the client is allowed to create new entries, it can initiate interactions with others by itself.

Once the agreements are concluded, ETHVAM clients are designed to automate and ETHVAM does not supply a direct communication channel between participants. Therefore, negotiations and general information exchange between the human participants has to take place elsewhere. However, the advantage of ETHVAM is that participants only have to agree on a mutual trusted SC and a process that can be formalized in Smart Contracts in order to automate its execution.

2.3.4 ENTRY CREATION

To create a new ETHVAM entry table, a client generally needs the permission of its SC to do so. If this is the case, the human participant in charge of the client designs a Smart Contract, defines the ACLs and a list of accessors for the entry. Also, a table name that is not already used in the Worldstate database has to be chosen in order to identify the entry. The client software can verify the syntax of the Smart Contract, but manual testing of the Smart Contract's functionality is strongly recommended because only a database administrator can delete an erroneous entry table. Since the complete table will be gone this will also delete all already completed updates. The revision number of a newly created entry must be 0 and the *parent's hash* field corresponds to the BLAKE2b hash of the table name. This makes it impossible even for database administrators to move an entry to a different table.

The read permission is especially problematic because it further grants access to all data elements of an entry to the client. Therefore, it is recommended to bundle only directly and necessarily linked data together into one entry. This also respects the principle of data economy and minimizes the impact of a data breach. In order to achieve more complex functionality and to mitigate the read access problem, multiple interacting entries can be used together. The write permissions on the other hand can be precisely controlled using the ACLs and the Smart Contract itself.

2 Encrypted Transaction-History Validation and Authentication Model

```
def encryptRow(self, unenc_row: UnencryptedRow) -> EncryptedRow:
    # ...

    # generate SIV libnacl_key and SIV nonce
    siv_key = get_random_bytes(64)
    siv_nonce = get_random_bytes(32)

    # setup SIV context
    siv = AES.new(siv_key, AES.MODE_SIV, nonce=siv_nonce)

    # encrypt the data
    ciphertext, digest_tag = siv.encrypt_and_digest(b_json_data)

    # combine ciphertext and digest_tag
    enc_data = digest_tag + ciphertext

    # combine siv_key and siv_nonce
    siv_secret = siv_key + siv_nonce

    enc_siv_secrets = []
    epemeral_secret_key = libnacl.public.SecretKey()

    # encrypt the siv secret with the reader keys (NaCl seal)
    accessors = Accessors.from_json(unenc_row.data['accessors'])
    for pk in accessors.list:
        nonce = BLAKE2b.new(data=epemeral_secret_key.pk + pk.pub,
                             digest_bytes=libnacl.crypto_box_NONCEBYTES).digest()

        ctxt = libnacl.crypto_box(siv_secret,
                                   nonce, pk.pub, epemeral_secret_key.sk)

        enc_siv_secrets.append(epemeral_secret_key.pk + ctxt)

    # add padding keys until next block of 10
    enc_siv_secrets_len = len(enc_siv_secrets)
    if enc_siv_secrets_len % 10 != 0:
        # ...
        padding = KDF.scrypt(Bytes.to_b64str(epemeral_secret_key.sk), '',
                               padding_size_bytes, 2**10, 8, 1)
        for kcur in range(0, padding_size_bytes, padding_key_size):
            enc_siv_secrets.append(epemeral_secret_key.pk +
                                   padding[kcur:kcur+padding_key_size])

    enc_keys = b"".join(enc_siv_secrets)

    # sign row
    msg_to_sign = EncryptedRow.calc_hash(unenc_row.table_name, unenc_row.rev,
                                         enc_data, enc_keys, unenc_row.parents_hash)
    signature = self.keypair.get_dual_secret().signature(msg_to_sign)

    return EncryptedRow(unenc_row.table_name, unenc_row.rev, enc_data,
                        enc_keys, unenc_row.parents_hash, signature, epemeral_secret_key.sk)
```

Listing 2.1: Cryptographic operations to encrypt an ETHVAM entry. For readability reasons all error handling code was removed.

When the entry is created, the client has to encrypt the entry's contents. An extract of the code used for this purpose is available in listing 2.1. To encrypt the entry, a client generates an AES-SIV key and a nonce. This key is encrypted with the public keys of all recipients and the resulting messages are stored in the keyslots. For this purpose, the client generates an ephemeral private signing key to be compliant with the NaCl seal function. Additionally, the ephemeral key is used to seed the script algorithm which generates the necessary keyslot padding data. The client finalizes the encrypted entry by signing the concatenation of revision number, encrypted entry contents, keyslots and the hash of the table name.

```
enc_siv_secrets = []

for validator_pk in self.settings['validators']:
    nonce = self.keystore.generate_nonce(libnacl.crypto_box_NONCEBYTES)
    enc_siv_secrets.append(libnacl.crypto_box(siv_secret,
        nonce, validator_pk.pub,
        self.keystore.get_private_key().priv) + nonce)
```

Listing 2.2: Snippet of the keyslot encryption code for proposals.

The proposal combines the serialized, encrypted Worldstate entry with the ephemeral private signing key and is encrypted in a similar way. In contrast to the entry data encryption, the client does not generate an ephemeral signing key which is shown in the code snippet of listing 2.2. Instead, the client uses its own private signing key to sign the keyslots for the validators, which removes the necessity for a separate signature. In the end, this encrypted proposal is stored in the client's table of the proposal database.

After the proposal is submitted, the responsible validator will eventually process and decrypt it. The first step in the validation process is to verify the signature of the proposed Worldstate entry using the public key of the creator that identified the table. The validator detects the creation attempt based on the revision number being 0. Then, it has to look up in the clients table of the SC if this client is allowed to create new entries. Afterwards, it checks if the proposed table name is free and verifies that the parent's hash field matches the proposed table name. Now, the proposed entry is decrypted and the validator will check the entries contents. First, it is verified that the author field matches the client that submitted the entry. Then, the timestamp will be checked for its RFC3339 compliance and if it is in the past. Because no Smart Contract can be executed, the history is empty and the validator only parses the attached code to check for syntax errors. The same applies to the ACLs which can only be verified

tested regarding the correctness of the structure and the expiry dates referring to the future. Afterwards, the accessors field is reviewed to contain all clients mentioned in the ACLs and the SC's validators whereby additional clients are allowed if they are participants of the SC. Finally, the validator uses the accessors list in combination with the ephemeral private signing key of the proposal to recreate the keyslots as well as the padding data and compares it to the proposed entry's keyslots field. If all checks are successful the new table is created and the proposal is removed.

2.3.5 ENTRY UPDATE

When a client updates an entry, it has to respect the rules of the ACL as well as the Smart Contract. As a prerequisite for this, the client is allowed to read the entry which is protected by encryption. The client must first retrieve the latest Worldstate database entry in the relevant table in order to change it. Then, it decrypts the entry and uses a Smart Contract interpreter to apply the desired changes. This interpreter runs the entry's code and retrieves needed additional Worldstate entries on demand. During this process, the interpreter will check the ACL compliance. If any operation fails due to insufficient rights or other faults, the interpreter will raise an error and the client is supposed to inform its administrator providing debug information. In the case of success, the interpreter eventually generates an updated version of the Worldstate entry. Next, the client will perform the same necessary cryptographic operations as in the entry creation process to encrypt the entry, generate the proposal and encrypt it as well.

After the submission to the proposal database, a responsible validator will perform the following steps to publish the desired Worldstate update. The validator verifies the signature of the proposed entry and after the decryption, it recognizes that a Worldstate update is requested on the basis of the revision number. Next, it looks up the Worldstate database to fetch the last entry of the respective Worldstate table and checks if the revision number of the proposed entry is incrementing the Worldstate. If these tests succeed, the validator decrypts the proposed Worldstate entry. The timestamp inside the entry must refer to a bygone point in time after the creation of the previous entry. Then, the validator uses the information of the history section in combination with the fetched Worldstate entry and the provided timestamp to execute the Smart Contract in the name of the author. This will generate another version of the proposed entry. During this process, ACL compliance is tested and timestamp

validation is performed. Now, all seven properties of the proposed entry are checked against the just generated version of this proposal. Next, the validator examines the ACL and makes sure that any client mentioned in the ACL is also in the accessors list. Last, the validator uses the ephemeral signing key and the accessors' field of the entry to recreate the keyslots and the random keyslot padding. The padding is reproducible because it was generated by using the private ephemeral signing key as input for a script based key derivation function. This allows the validator to ensure that no additional entities have read access to the entry. If any of these tests fail, the validator will reject the proposal. Furthermore, it alerts the author of the entry and, in case of a security violation, the administrator of the SC. Otherwise, the validator appends its signature to the proposed entry and publishes it in the Worldstate database. Finally, the validator removes the processed proposal from the proposal database. In conclusion, the calculations for the update process involve only two computers which is a lot more efficient and energy saving than an update on a Blockchain.

2.3.6 CHANGE CONTROL AND SMART CONTRACTS

This section describes the different possibilities to control the update process. ETHVAM comes with two options to describe and enforce change control. On the one hand, Access Control Lists (ACL) are used to define basic change restrictions on the basis of an entry's contents. On the other hand, Smart Contracts can implement complex change control rules including dependencies on other Worldstate entries.

ETHVAM provides two ACLs per entry. One controls which Smart Contract functions a client can execute and the other defines which data the client can change.

The function ACL requires a purely procedural Smart Contract language. Furthermore, this allows to create functions that act like clauses of a contract and define an independent program flow. These entry functions of a Smart Contract are called *clauses* in the following. Since the execution of clauses changes the Worldstate, they should only be executed by authorized clients. The function ACL defines which clauses can be executed by which clients. Each clause is linked to a list of authorized clients which entries consist of client identifier, expiry timestamp and a delegation parameter. Thus, executive permissions can be limited in their validity. The delegation parameter specifies if this permission is delegable to other clients through certifications.

function name 1	client 1	expiry date	delegable
	client 2	expiry date	delegable
		⋮	
function name 2	⋮		
⋮			

Figure 2.4: Visualization of the function ACL layout.

The data ACL structure is similar but, instead of function names, it references the data objects of the regarding Worldstate entry. Data objects, in this context, are not only the data used by the Smart Contract but also the accessors list, the Smart Contract’s code and even the ACL itself. In short, all information of an entry that can be changed by Smart Contracts is subject to the restrictions of the data ACL.

Smart Contracts in ETHVAM are used to define distinct update procedures for the data of an entry. They can consist of various different clauses and provide the functional logic to apply desired changes. Thus, a Smart Contract can enforce much more complex restrictions than an ACL. For instance, a Smart Contract can restrict updates depending on other Worldstate entries’ data. This requires the updating client to also have read access to the referenced Worldstate entry. Smart Contracts can in fact enforce the same restrictions as the ACL but with the downside that no verification of feasibility can be performed. In the worst case, this can lead to a deadlocked entry. Therefore, it is recommended to only use Smart Contracts for restrictions when the ACLs are insufficient. In most cases, it is the better approach to define multiple clauses instead of using the client’s identifier to realize restrictions.

The Smart Contracts’ functionality is not only useful to separate privileges but also to separate different use cases. For instance, a contract that controls deliveries can implement clauses in favor of the buyer and seller. On the buyer’s side, a clause can define penalties for deferred delivery and on the seller’s side another clause could forward fees in case of the violation of a purchase guarantee. Furthermore, a Smart Contract can have a clause that adds additional clients to the accessors list and adapt the ACLs for the new clients. It is even possible to change the Smart Contract to add or modify clauses in order to adapt to new requirements. To realize all these abilities, the Smart Contract language has to provide the necessary building blocks to do the calculations and access the wordstate database.

Smart Contract languages already in use are optimized for Blockchain environments or have been specially adapted to them. None of them could be used to interface with distributed databases without major changes. Therefore, the *Smart Contract Application Language for Databases* (SCALD) was designed to be a procedural proof of concept language for Smart Contracts on distributed databases. As Smart Contracts are only used for data transformations based on process models, a non Turing complete language is sufficient. Furthermore, a domain specific language is advantageous from the security perspective because of its limited scope. The potential functionality of malware is limited and the risk that validators are compromised by malicious code is minimized. SCALD, the proof of concept language for ETHVAM Smart Contracts, is presented in the next Chapter.

2.3.7 GOALS ACHIEVED

In the beginning of this section, a list of goals were presented which will now be evaluated.

The Cockroach database itself can grow almost infinitely by adding new nodes anywhere on the globe, which also allows the number of clients to grow without upper limit. Furthermore, it is possible to introduce as many security contexts and validators as needed. Therefore, the **scalability** goal is reached. Cockroach's ability to redistribute the data in case of failing nodes or datacenters contributes to the **viability** of ETHVAM, but if database nodes act malicious, the database will be compromised. Complete database backups are required to ensure disaster recovery and mitigate this risk. A similar problem arises on the security context level, but it might be possible to implement an efficient Byzantine fault resilient validation process with further research.

The **secrecy** of the database entries is secured under the assumption that the validators are not using their read privileges for other purposes than the verification of entries. Only clients that are in the accessors list can read an entry. The goal of **verifiability** is also achieved on the database layout level. The AES-SIV mode of encryption ensures that any change to the encrypted data will result in a decryption error and the signature of the whole Worldstate entry makes all other fields tamper-proof. The related goal of **accountability** is also realized due to the NaCl signatures of the Worldstate database and the verified author field in each entry's data. It is

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important for the accountability as well as for the verifiability that clients check the entry's signature.

The Smart Contract's flexibility allows almost all processes to be modeled in one or more Worldstate entries. Entries can depend on each other and modify themselves in all their active properties. This provides **plasticity** but requires careful planning and testing during the design. Validators check each proposed entry for errors as well as for ACL and Smart Contract compliance before the Worldstate is updated. Thus, the **validity of entries** is ensured, but even valid entries can cause deadlocks due to flawed Smart Contracts or ACL settings. The same checking process ensures that **change control** is enforced. Furthermore, each validation process requires the replication of the process that led to its proposal. This provides a **genuine history** as long as the database administrator does not interfere with the append-only property of the Worldstate database.

Theoretically, ETHVAM fulfills all desired design goals except for the viability. For this reason, the next section examines the effects of malicious system interferences as part of a security analysis to ascertain the overall security properties of ETHVAM.

2.4 SECURITY ANALYSIS

This section deals with the security model of ETHVAM and analyzes the effects of malicious abuse of ETHVAM's components. The different security breaches are discussed in the subsequent sections.

2.4.1 MALICIOUS SMART CONTRACT

A malicious Smart Contract can be used for fraud, information leakage or to cause a deadlock. It can implement functionality that changes the behavior of clients in a non intended way. Furthermore, it can introduce a special clause that locks out other clients when triggered. Such activities can only be reverted by asking the database administrator to delete the affected entries. This has to be done carefully and is probably time consuming but in contrast to Blockchain systems a possible solution.

If a Smart Contract is created with malicious intent, it can try to hide its harmful functionality through obfuscation. The Smart Contract language SCALD presented in the next chapter tries to give an attacker as few options as possible to do so. However, the more complex a Smart Contracts is, the less likely such malicious functionality is detected.

Therefore, to mitigate these risks, each participant should proofread all Smart Contracts affecting them and inform the responsible security context administrator of any suspicions. Due to the accountable nature of ETHVAM Worldstate entries, an attacker can be spotted and in consequence their permissions can be revoked.

2.4.2 MALICIOUS CLIENT

The clients are the most vulnerable part of ETHVAM because they are likely administrated by people who are not trained in IT-security. Moreover, clients automatize processes and therefore are likely to be localized in an insecure location.

If a client acts in a harmful way, this has multiple implications: First, the secrecy of all entries the client has access to can be violated. Second, an attacker can use the clients ability to submit proposals to change entries in a way that leads to wrong

information in the Worldstate entries to which the client has change rights. If the client is permitted to change the ACLs or the Smart Contract, it is easy for an attacker to cause a deadlock in these entries. Third, if the affected client has permission to create new entries, the same considerations apply as in the case of a malicious Smart Contract. Fourth, the attacker can submit a high number of proposals which will result in big workloads for the validators. However, validators can process proposals multithreaded with one thread per client table. Thus, only the throughput of the validators will be affected. When the validator encounters a faulty proposal, it will move it to a separate database and skip all other proposals of this client in the current validation queue. Unfortunately, if the attacker can create arbitrary numbers of valid proposals, the validators will each dedicate a thread to the affected client which will use up much more validator resources. In the extreme case that multiple clients of a security context (SC) are under the attacker's control this can lead to a denial of service of the affected SC. Administrators can take action against this by configuring validators to not further process the proposals of a client after a certain number of incorrect proposals was reviewed.

2.4.3 MALICIOUS PROPOSAL OR WORLDSTATE DATABASE

If just the proposal database becomes compromised, the attacker can delete all new proposals, which will result in a denial of service. Furthermore, a single client can be targeted by an attacker in this position because all proposals of this client can be suppressed. This could remain undetected for a longer time due to the fact that clients are operating automatically and a removed proposal will not lead to an error or alert. Without further breaches, however, an attacker in the proposal database cannot read or manipulate any Worldstate entries.

An attacker with administrative access to the Worldstate database can do more damage to the system. They can delete Worldstate entries or even the complete database causing a denial of service and data loss. A less aggressive attacker can revoke already accepted changes or completely delete certain tables. Still, from this position, no manipulated entry can be placed or illicitly read. To recover from such an attack, a database backup has to be restored, which will probably cause data loss and temporary unavailability of the database.

To prevent such incidents, database administrators should be trained in IT-security and handle their credentials with great care. Unfortunately, CockroachDB does not support two factor authentication but, it allows to rotate certificates in order to recover from a breach.

2.4.4 MALICIOUS DATABASE NODE

If an attacker gains control over the actual computer a CockroachDB node is running on, they could inflict serious damage to ETHVAM. The control over a database node grants administrative privileges. Therefore, all attacks on the databases are possible from this position. Furthermore, the database software itself can be attacked. This can give an attacker control over other database nodes. As a ray of hope for the system, even an attacker with this much power cannot read nor manipulate database entries due to the encryption scheme of ETHVAM.

Recovering from an incident where the attacker got access to a database node is tedious. The affected computer needs a new setup because it is possible that malware was hidden. If there is any suspicion that the attacker gained access to other nodes too, they need a new setup as well. Furthermore, all access keys need to be rotated and the database has to be recovered.

In consequence, the database nodes should be located in a safe environment on distinct root servers. The attack surface of the database nodes has to be minimized to provide a reasonable security level for ETHVAM. Also, IT-security training should be mandatory for the node administrators.

2.4.5 MALICIOUS CERTIFICATION AUTHORITY

In another severe scenario for ETHVAM, an attacker gains control over the certification authority. The knowledge about the CA's keys will allow administrative access to the databases with all consequences. Nonetheless, the secrecy and authenticity of database entries is maintained even in this case. Because the CA only governs database access, but never comes into contact with the encryption keys of the entries, an attacker cannot make valid changes to the Worldstate.

2 Encrypted Transaction-History Validation and Authentication Model

If not only the CA's keys but also the communication identity of the CA is abused, the attacker can try to impersonate the CA. However, as long as the security context administrators do not hand encryption keys or other sensitive information over, no additional harm can be done. To ensure this security level, SC administrators must never be asked to provide key material. Moreover, the administration of the CA and database nodes must be strictly separated from the validator and security context administration.

To recover from this situation, a complete reset of the database has to be performed. All keys must be regenerated and rolled out and finally the database has to be restored from a recent backup.

2.4.6 MALICIOUS VALIDATOR

A security breach that involves the hostile takeover of a validator has to be considered most severe. If the capabilities of a validator are abused, it can submit arbitrary entries into the Worldstate database. This can cause denial of service to all security contexts.

In the security context of the affected validator, an attacker can read all entries. Furthermore, it is possible to create made up entries, from which code will be eventually executed by the SC's clients. An attack with validator permissions can subvert the authenticity and accountability of changes by creating a custom client key. Additionally, the attacker can remove all proposals of members of the affected security context, therefore preventing other validators to interfere with their malicious actions. Consequently, the complete security context could be taken over. This scenario is without doubt one of the worst for ETHVAM's security and reveals the potential for great damage.

Clients could spot such made up entries by performing additional history checks for each retrieved Worldstate entry. This results in a tradeoff situation with security on the one side and resource consumption as well as throughput on the other side. Unfortunately, these checks are impossible for newly created entries because they have no history at creation time.

A recovery plan must consider the complete SC as compromised and roll back all unauthorized Worldstate changes. All client administrators of the affected SC have to

be informed about the leakage of information. Since, validators can only add entries to the Worldstate, unauthorized changes can be detected by recalculating and checking all Worldstate entries against their history. To spot made up entries, the complete Worldstate database has to be scanned and because of ETHVAM's encryption scheme, all SCs have to cooperate. An entry that cannot be decrypted by any validator or originates from an unknown author can be considered as fabrication.

In consequence, the SC administrators bear great responsibility. Validators must be secured physically as well as administrated with security in mind. The security considerations regarding database nodes must also apply here.

2.5 COMPARISON AND RÉSUMÉ

With ETHVAM, a first step was achieved in the research and development of a Smart Contract System for distributed databases. The theoretically outstanding scalability should be backed up by measurements in further research and possible bottlenecks need to be identified. Since only two computers have to perform the resource-intensive calculations for a database update, the energy efficiency and throughput should be better compared to Blockchain systems. A new system was created which is Blockchain-like but provides deliberately weaker guarantees for the genuine history of datasets. In contrast to Blockchain systems, entries can be deleted in exceptional cases, allowing malicious or incorrect contracts to be revised.

One of the drawbacks of ETHVAM in comparison to Blockchain systems, is its higher vulnerability to denial of service attacks. Due to the fact that the entire contents of the database are not stored on all participating network nodes, sensitive points which allow a denial of service attack are inevitable.

The confidentiality, integrity and accountability of the entries can also be ensured in most of the examined attack scenarios. However, the trust position of the validators is a security risk. A successful attack on the administrators or validators of a security context undermines many of the security features that ETHVAM advocates and cannot be detected trivially. The privilege separation between the administrators of the databases and the security contexts is crucial for ETHVAM's overall security and has to be stressed here. A backup strategy that allows the database to be restored in the event of a disaster is equally important.

In addition to improving the security properties, further research could focus on the implementation of self-executing Smart Contracts without delegating even more responsibility to the validators.

3 SMART CONTRACT APPLICATION LANGUAGE FOR DATABASES

The acronym SCALD stands for “Smart Contract Application Language for (distributed) Databases”.

SCALD is a Turing incomplete¹ [39], domain-specific language designed for exploring the possibilities of Smart Contracts on distributed databases. It was built to automate data transformation in ETHVAM systems and directly interact with the distributed database. Furthermore, it aims to describe data transformation procedures in a way that is not only easy to write, but also simple to be verified by human beings. It allows authors to specify in which way and under which circumstances data is supplemented, updated or deleted². The language is inspired by the concept with which Smart Contracts are defined in Blockchain projects such as Ethereum [40] or Hyperledger [2] and transfers it to ETHVAM systems.

During the design of SCALD’s grammar, different parser generators were evaluated and in the end Lark’s [41] LALR-parser [42] became the foundation of SCALD. The grammar features the imperative procedural programming paradigm and is inspired by the Python [43] programming language as well as influenced by C. A Python interpreter, equipped with the ability to directly interact with database entries of ETHVAM systems, was developed to run code written in SCALD. The following sections will explain these decisions and the development of the language. The source code is available under <https://emcl-gitlab.iwr.uni-heidelberg.de/olaf.pichler/masterthesis/> and is licensed under the “European Union Public Licence version 1.2” [44].

¹In fact, SCALD in combination with the attached database forms a Turing complete system, but an SCALD program itself remains Turing incomplete.

²The data remains in the previous records and therefore the accessors can read it, but becomes unavailable in future entries.

3.1 DEVELOPMENT

This section introduces the concepts of “Turing completeness” and “Backus Naur form” which are crucial for the following parts. Afterwards it describes the development of SCALD’s grammar and syntax.

3.1.1 TURING COMPLETENESS

The Turing completeness of a system describes its universal programming capability. More precisely, Turing completeness in computability theory is the ability of a programming language or other logical system to compute all functions that a universal Turing machine can compute. Although such machines are physically impossible because they would require infinite memory, computers and programming languages that would be universally capable if they had infinite memory are called Turing complete.

Turing complete systems are proven to always be affected by the halting problem [45], that is to say, no algorithm exists that can make a statement about the terminality of arbitrary source codes.

3.1.2 BACKUS NAUR FORM

The Backus Naur form (BNF) is a formal metalanguage to describe context free grammars and is used to define the syntax of programming languages. It was introduced by John W. Backus and Peter Naur in the “Algol 60 Report” and made it possible to formally describe a programming language.

The BNF defines terminals and non terminals. Non terminals are rewrite rules that define substitutions which can be applied recursively to generate new sequences. In contrast, terminals are symbols that are not further resolved like digit or character literals.

```
<digit without zero> ::= "1"|"2"|"3"|"4"|"5"|"6"|"7"|"8"|"9"  
<digit> ::= "0" | <digit without zero>  
<digit sequence> ::= <digit> | <digit> <digit sequence>  
<positive integer> ::= <digit without zero>  
| <digit without zero> <digit sequence>
```

Listing 3.1: Example of the Backus Naur form.

An advancement of the BNF is the so called “extended Backus Naur form” [46]. Alike in BNF, production rules define non terminal symbols out of an alphabet of terminal symbols and already defined non terminal symbols. The EBNF extends the notation by providing syntax to annotate repetition, grouping and optionality. Some parsers further extend this by allowing the inline definition of terminal strings through regular expressions. Furthermore, other control sequences are sometimes introduced which results in a big number of EBNF variants.

```
digit_without_zero = "1" | "2" | "3" | "4" | "5" | "6" | "7" | "8" | "9" ;
digit              = "0" | digit_without_zero ;
positive_integer  = digit_without_zero, { digit } ;
```

Listing 3.2: Example of the extended Backus Naur form.

3.1.3 GRAMMAR

After the need for a distinct programming language for Smart Contracts was identified, the research for a feasible grammar began as a first step. In the beginning, JavaScript was considered as a foundation because the Hyperledger [2] project is already using it for Smart Contracts. However, JavaScript in its simplicity does not provide strong typing or distinct contexts for functions. Furthermore, JavaScript only defines objects and does not support procedural programming. Therefore, it was found to be inappropriate for ETHVAM without major changes. Instead, the choice was made to use Python. This idea emerged since Python is a very beginner friendly and also very mighty tool.

A simple grammar and syntax was necessary due to the time limitations of this project. This premise led to the concept of a procedural language which allows structured programming while keeping the process of parsing and in particular interpreting code easy. A downside of Python is the need to consider whitespaces during the parsing process. For this reason, C was taken for inspiration as the best-known representative of procedural languages. In C, each statement is terminated by a semicolon and associated commands are enclosed in curly braces. This simplifies the parsing of C programs because all whitespaces can safely be ignored by the parser. Due to this advantage, these grammatical characteristics of C have been incorporated into the design of SCALD. These deliberations about the desired syntax led to the idea of combining the easy to parse syntax of C with a dynamic but strong type system well known from the Python programming language. Therefore, Python and C became the foundation of SCALD and Python also became the language of choice for the interpreter.

3.1.4 PARSER

The next step was the search for a parser generator. Initial attempts were made with Flex and Bison [47] because these programs are open-source reimplementations of the POSIX standard tools Lex and Yacc [48]. It quickly became clear that these generators are inexpedient because the programs require to be used in combination with C, which would dramatically increase the complexity of the project. Even though the attempt was abandoned, a list of tokens a lexer needs to recognize was developed during the process. Furthermore, describing the language's grammar in terms of the Backus–Naur form, led to a deeper understanding of the principles of lexing and parsing, which became very helpful for the following steps of development.

The next approach was taken using Python Lex-Yacc (PLY) [49], an implementation of Lex and Yacc parsing tools for Python. In this phase, a first grammar was drafted, of which an excerpt can be seen in figure 3.1. During this time, many of the conditions for SCALD to become useful were identified. The needed set of operators was defined and the decision to use operator representations, alike those in the C programming language, was made. This early grammar already planned to realize a sort of standard library through built-in functions which are identified by parser tokens, a concept still used in current versions. Also, the idea to realize ETHVAM database interactions through built-ins emerged.

A big shift in the concept took place when it was discovered that SCALD does not need to be Turing complete to fulfill its purpose. Neither the data transformations nor the logical structures of usual Smart Contracts require functionality from Turing complete languages. Furthermore, this step towards a completely domain-specific language had multiple advantages. Firstly, the interpreter design became much simpler because almost all edge cases that could allow malicious code execution inside the interpreter could be eliminated. Secondly, there is no halting problem in a non Turing complete language. Therefore, it can be proven that every SCALD program will terminate in finite time. Finally, programs can only reach a certain amount of complexity, which makes automatic contract validation simple and less error-prone. This also helps humans to easily understand and audit Smart Contracts, which is crucial to build trust in such a system.

Figure 3.1: Part of the grammar draft of SCALD during the test of PLY.

One problem still remained because PLY is providing a lexer and a parser generator, but does not provide users with neither a parse tree nor an abstract syntax tree (AST). Thus, to build an interpreter, one first needs to program PLY in order to generate an AST and then write an interpreter using the AST as input. This makes developing a grammar further very inconvenient and slow once it is implemented. However, during the research about abstract syntax trees, the Lark [41] parser project was discovered. It combines a modern lexer and parser generator which directly outputs a parse tree. In contrary to Bison and PLY, Lark uses a variant of the extended Backus–Naur form (EBNF), which makes it easier and less error-prone to formulate complex grammars. Regular expressions can be used to describe tokens and terminal definitons can be inlined. In addition, it has the ability to reshape the parse tree into an AST and so removes the need for this time-consuming activity. All in all, the usage of Lark tremendously accelerated development and therefore, Lark was found to be the superior parsing solution³.

³Also notable but for this project less important properties are that the used LALR(1) parser is one of the fastest parses available and that the Earley parser, which is also supported, is capable of any context free grammar.

3.2 SYNTAX AND ARCHITECTURE

The architecture of SCALD is structured in three distinct logical layers, building on each other. On the top level, functions encapsulate program logic and provide the ability to reuse and structure code. The middle level is used for statements, managing the program flow and state changes. The final level contains expressions that are logical atoms of SCALD required for the evaluation of program code. This section will discuss these layers and close with a look at the type system of SCALD.

3.2.1 FUNCTIONS

Functions are the root elements of SCALD's architecture so that every source file is at first a collection of function definitions. Function definitions are only possible in the outer most context of a source file and they cannot overlap or encapsulate each other.⁴ To maintain Turing incompleteness, the interpreter will check at each function call if another instance of the called function is already on the stack. If so, it prevents the call and raises an exception.

```

root : function+
function : function_name "(" param_list ")" function_body
param_list : (param ("," param)*)?
function_body : "{" statement+ "}"
function_name : ID
?param : ID

```

Listing 3.3: Function grammar.

As shown in listing 3.3, every function is defined through an identifier, a list of parameters and a function body. Every identifier refers to a distinct name defined in the scope of the token `ID` : `/[A-Za-z_][\w_]*/`. Functions are identified by their names. For that reason, they cannot be overloaded or shadowed. Parameters will be made available inside the function as predefined variables named after the corresponding *param* identifier. The function body holds the statements about to be executed. The last executed statement has to be a return statement. This is motivated by the type system of SCALD that does not support otherwise necessary empty values.

⁴In practice, the source of a SCALD program is meant to be obtained as part of a Smart Contract from the database.

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In contrary to C, where every program executes `int main()` at foremost, authors of SCALD can freely choose the entry function. Furthermore, they can provide users with multiple entry functions in order to realize complex contracts. In general, a source file can be entered at any defined function, but the ACL associated with the source code provides the possibility to restrict users to only enter the code at specific functions⁵. However, an entry function is supposed to return a Boolean that provides information about the fulfillment of the contract's conditions. `False` is returned if any requirements of the contract were not satisfied and `True` if all contract terms are fulfilled.

Code example:

```
square(x){
  x2 = x*x;
  return x2;
}
/* This is the entry function of this contract */
write_sqared(number){
  return write("squared_number", square(number));
}
```

In this example, the entry function was marked by a comment in the style of C block comments, like all comments in SCALD.

Each function body defines its own closed scope for variables. From outside the function, only parameters and return values interact with this scope. In the given example, it would not be possible for any other function than `square` to gain access to `x2`. The requirement for entry functions is also fulfilled in the example because the built-in `write` returns a Boolean to indicate if the operation is permitted for the executing user.

3.2.2 STATEMENTS

Inside a function body statements control the program flow. They enable branching, for-loops, the evaluation of expressions and passing back values from functions. In listing 3.4, the EBNF definitions of the four types of statements are given. Furthermore the enumeration below provides a detailed description of the properties of each statement type.

⁵This is explained in more detail in section 3.3.1.

```
statement : "return" expression ";" -> return_statement
          | if_block elif_block* [else_block] -> if_statement
          | "for" "(" for_arguments ")" statement_list -> for_statement
          | expression ";" -> eval_statement
```

Listing 3.4: Statement grammar.

1. A *return* statement evaluates the given expression and passes the result back to the higher level function. When this statement is reached, the current function is immediately terminated.
2. Conditional branches are defined through *if* statements. They always start with **if** followed by a condition in brackets. Any number of **elif** blocks are allowed to test additional conditions. Finally, the optional **else** block catches if no previous condition has matched.

```
if (name=="Homer") {message="I like Donuts";}
elif (name=="Lisa") {message="I want to play Saxophon";}
elif (name=="Bart") {message="Eat my shorts";}
else {message="Springfield is awesome";}

```

3. Loops are defined by *for* statements and can iterate over container elements as well as ranges. Loops are restricted to a number of iterations known in advance to preserve SCALD's Turing incompleteness. The sequence of values a loop variable will iterate over is fixed before the first evaluation of the loop's body and therefore cannot be changed, once the loop is entered. The first argument after the **for** is always the identifier of the loop variable. This identifier must not be previously defined in the surrounding context, meaning that no other variable of the function can be overwritten or shadowed by the loop variable.

The next argument can either be a container type, thus *str*, *dict* or *vec*, or a range. In case a container type is given, the loop variable will iterate over the contents of the container⁶. However, the container itself will remain mutable.

Ranges, on the other hand, always require numbers as arguments. The most simple range definition is achieved by passing a positive number as argument. This will cause the loop variable to start at zero and keep incrementing by one as long as it is smaller than the passed number. If two numbers are passed, they define a range with start and end. Under the condition that the first passed number is smaller than the second one, the loop variable will iterate from the smaller with step size 1 until it reaches or exceeds the second number. The most

⁶When a *dict* is passed in, the loop will iterate over the keys of the hash map.

complex range definitions require three arguments. At first, the start value, then the end value and finally the step size. This allows counting down as well as non integer step sizes.

```
for(name, ["Alice", "Bob"]) {
  print("Hello ", name, "!");
}
/* Start a countdown */
for(counter, 10, 0, -0.1) {
  print("T minus ", counter);
}
```

Listing 3.5: Example of loop use cases.

4. The purpose of *eval* statements is the evaluation of expressions and they always require a terminating semicolon to indicate the end of the statement. The next section will explain these expressions in more detail.

3.2.3 EXPRESSIONS

The most varied part of SCALD's architecture are expressions; they are used to realize:

- variable definition and assignment
- variable access
- type determination and casts
- chaining of operations
- mathematical and logical operators
- function and built-in calls
- database interactions
- interpreting constants and literals

This part will only cover the grammatical peculiarities of expressions. For a complete list of the available built-ins, please refer to section [3.3.2](#).

One of the key challenges of parsing expressions was the need for operator precedence. Because a left-to-right parser is used with SCALD, the right operand of the EBNF rule is susceptible to misinterpretations.

This chain of expressions

$$2 * 3 + 4$$

will serve as an example. Without a precedence model, they would be parsed as

$$\text{multiply}(2, \text{add}(3, 4))$$

and the resulting value 14 is certainly not the desired solution of this combined expression.

Since the parser has no information about precedence rules and the LALR(1) parser does not support rule priorities on its own, a precedence model described in EBNF was developed. For this purpose, the C precedence model [50] was used as a reference. To implement this precedence model, ten hierarchically arranged EBNF rules were used. Each rule of the precedence model defines a precedence level. A higher precedence level takes priority over lower precedence levels. The right side of a precedence rule contains expressions of the same priority level, whereas on the left side, only expressions of a higher precedence level are allowed.

```
?expression_5 : expression_6
                | expression_5 "+" expression_6 -> add
                | expression_5 "-" expression_6 -> subtract
?expression_6 : expression_7
                | expression_6 "*" expression_7 -> multiply
                | expression_6 "/" expression_7 -> divide
                | expression_6 "%" expression_7 -> modulo
```

Listing 3.6: Excerpt of the precedence model definition.

The size of the precedence model definition is too big to be feasibly cited in its entirety⁷, but an excerpt will be used here in combination with the given problem as a representative example of a solution. In listing 3.6, the realization of the priority of multiplication operations over addition operations is displayed. The precedence model defines the rules in such a way that the parser cannot use an expression of rank five as the right side of a multiplication. Thus, this conflict between the mathematically correct and the parsed order of operations could be resolved. Table 3.1 shows a list of all expression types and operators corresponding to their precedence.

⁷See Appendix [SCALD's Grammar](#).

precedence level	operators and expression types	operator
1	assignment operations	=
2	logical or	
3	logical and	&&
4	equality and inequality	== !=
5	size comparison	> >= < <=
6	addition and subtraction	+ -
7	multiplication and division	* / %
8	unary minus and logical negation	- !
9	<i>vec</i> and <i>dict</i> definitions, brackets	[] [:] ()
10	literal evaluation, variable access built-ins, function call	

Table 3.1: Precedence order of operations.

3.2.4 TYPES

The type system of SCALD was specifically chosen to be compatible with the JSON [37] serialization format. This is important for representing and organizing the data that is supposed to be stored in the database.

Each expression will evaluate into a result of one distinct type. As a result, a variable's type is determined at the same moment a value is assigned to it. At all times, the type of a variable is therefore unambiguous. A list of all available types is presented in table 3.2. The first three entries refer to the most basic types of variables. Types *int*, *float* and *bool* are considered simple types in comparison to the more complex container types. Raw values of simple types as well as *str* literals are directly recognized as tokens by the parser and immediately converted into a machine representation during the parsing process.

Container types, on the other hand, can embed multiple values and come with the ability to address and change their contents individually. They can also be used to define iteration sequences for loops. Contents of types *str* and *vec* can be accessed by an integer index and loops will iterate directly over the contents they enclose. A type *str*, however, can only hold characters represented as substrings. The *vec* type has a similar behavior. It can contain multiple values of a distinct type, but does not support mixed type contents. This tradeoff was accepted to allow mathematical

type	specifier	size	occurrence in code
integer	int	64 bit	myint = -3;
floating-point number	float	64 bit	myfloat = 1.23;
boolean	bool	1 bit	mybool = True;
string	str	variable	mystr = "hello world";
list / vector	vec	variable	myvec = [1, 2, 3];
hash map	dict	variable	mydict = ["n":"Bob","a":31];

Table 3.2: The types supported by SCALD.

functions to use values of type *vec* as input, which allows more efficient calculation and enunciation of mathematical problems.

In contrast, variables of type *dict* can contain values of any type at the same time. In addition, *dict* acts as a key-value store linking keys of type *str* to arbitrary values. Internally, a hash map realizes this functionality. One characteristic attribute of *dict* is its behavior as loop defining container. The loop variable will iterate over a sequence of the *dict*'s keys.

3.3 INTERPRETER SPECIALTIES

During the interpreting of source code, some of the special properties of SCALD must receive attention. One of the key features of SCALD is its ability to directly interact with a system that implements the *Encrypted Transaction-History Validation and Authentication Model* described in chapter 2. This requires information and functionality not naturally available in the scope of the interpreter and these therefore must be provided from outside. Furthermore, SCALD code cannot link to external resources to include additional functionality. For this reason, the interpreter has to implement a lot of basic and advanced algorithms as built-ins. Table 3.3 shows a list of SCALD's currently available built-ins.

3.3.1 ACL VALIDATION AND DATABASE INTERACTION

ETHVAM requires SCALD to enforce compliance with the applying access control lists during the interpretation process. At each run, two ACLs have to be considered. The first concerns the entry function and describes which functions can be initially called by which client. This has to be checked before the interpreter is instructed to execute the function in question. On the contrary, the second ACL needs to be checked at runtime because it defines which data can be updated by whom. This requirement leads to the question how SCALD can interact with the ETHVAM database.

A database interface provides the desired functionality and exposes functions to query the database for needed information as well as scheduling updates of the dataset. This interface needs the data ACL and it implements:

- **whoami()** returns the hexadecimal encoded identifier of the clients public key.
- **read_local(key)** reads the value referenced by *key* of the same entry the executed code belongs to.
- **read_global(table_name, revision, key)** queries the database to access the entry identified by *table_name* and *revision*. Then, it tries to decrypt the entry with the client's credentials. If successful, the client has the permission to read data out of this entry.

- **read_last_global(table_name, key)** has the same function as the previous one but always queries the last entry of the desired table.
- **write_data(key, value)** checks with the ACL if the client is allowed to write data identified by *key*. If so, the key value pair is stored in order for it to be included in the resulting proposal entry.
- **update_code(...)** is a potential but not implemented feature that allows the contract's code to change itself.
- **update_acl(...)** is a potential but not implemented feature that provides the ability to update the access control lists.
- **update_accessors(...)** is a potential but not implemented feature that provides the ability to change the list of clients that have read access to the current entry.

3.3.2 BUILT-IN FUNCTIONS

Built-in functions extend the capabilities of SCALD. They provide a standard library and help to overcome some of the limitations of Turing incomplete languages. Various tasks are already covered, but the intended scope is far from being complete. Besides its advantages, SCALD's Turing incompleteness prevents the ability to implement most of the efficient algorithms programmers are currently used to. However, for the reason that SCALD is a domain specific language, there is no need to implement complex algorithms in SCALD itself and therefore this was never a design goal. SCALD's built-in functions provide algorithms written in general purpose languages that are optimized for performance. The vast scope built-ins can cover also overcomes the need for linking other source code. This is especially beneficial when Smart Contracts are audited because it further limits complexity and thus the possibility to sneak in malicious logic.

Built-in functions are defined directly in the grammar of SCALD so they need to be implemented by the interpreter. Contrary to normal functions, built-ins are overloaded when it is reasonable. A unique grammar identifies them and makes them recognizable to the parser, which will assign a unique name to them which enables the interpreter to use the correct implementation. Nonetheless, the conduct of the

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built-in implementations needs to be well tested to prevent unsupported types and unexpected behavior from being included into SCALD.

Built-in functions are used in the same way as normal functions and they also cannot be shadowed by redefinition, which is especially necessary to keep proofreading of Smart Contracts as easy as possible. Although, those built-ins that implement the database interactions were already discussed in the previous section, the remaining more general ones are taken into account here. For a full list, please refer to table 3.3.

First, basic mathematical operations were implemented alongside trigonometric and hyperbolic functions. All these functions are capable of operating on vectors as well as with *int* and *float* values. Even so, it is expected that the current math functionality is not enough for SCALD to be used in real world applications. An option to define and initialize arrays of any size without the need to use loops is missing. Functions determining the minimal and maximal values of vectors and algorithms for statistics and linear algebra would also be desirable. In general, a time type with the functionality to compare and represent time deltas was identified to be beneficial. Likewise, regular expressions could be helpful to work with string data and there should be functions providing information about the client on whose behalf the source code is executed. Basic array manipulation is available, but additional functionality is probably needed. Presumably, more classes of missing functionality would be identified during a real world test. The planned and not yet implemented write functions require additional research to become aware of the implications these options will have on the security of ETHVAM.

built-in	description
fact (<i>x</i>)	calculates the factorial of <i>x</i>
pow (<i>x</i> , <i>y</i>)	calculates x^y
sqrt (<i>x</i>) sqrt (<i>x</i> , <i>n</i>)	calculates \sqrt{x} , respectively $\sqrt[n]{x}$
exp (<i>x</i>)	calculates the exponent of Euler's number e^x
log (<i>x</i>)	calculates the natural logarithm of <i>x</i>
log2 (<i>x</i>)	calculates the logarithm to base 2 of <i>x</i>
log10 (<i>x</i>)	calculates the logarithm to base 10 of <i>x</i>
PI	is a macro for 3.141592653589793
sin (<i>x</i>)	calculates the sine of <i>x</i>
cos (<i>x</i>)	calculates the cosine of <i>x</i>
tan (<i>x</i>)	calculates the tangent of <i>x</i>
arcsin (<i>x</i>)	calculates the arcus sine of <i>x</i>
arccos (<i>x</i>)	calculates the arcus cosine of <i>x</i>
arctan (<i>x</i>) arctan (<i>y</i> , <i>x</i>)	calculates the arcus tangent of <i>x</i> , respectively the 2-argument arcus tangent
sinh (<i>x</i>)	calculates the hyperbolic sine of <i>x</i>
cosh (<i>x</i>)	calculates the hyperbolic cosine of <i>x</i>
tanh (<i>x</i>)	calculates the hyperbolic tangent of <i>x</i>
arcsinh (<i>x</i>)	calculates the hyperbolic arcus sine of <i>x</i>
arccosh (<i>x</i>)	calculates the hyperbolic arcus cosine of <i>x</i>
arctanh (<i>x</i>)	calculates the hyperbolic arcus tangent of <i>x</i>
type (<i>arg</i>)	returns the type of the given argument as <i>str</i>
int (<i>arg</i>)	if possible converts the argument into a <i>int</i>
float (<i>arg</i>)	if possible converts the argument into a <i>float</i>
bool (<i>arg</i>)	if possible converts the argument into a <i>bool</i>
str (<i>arg</i>)	converts the argument into a <i>str</i>
del (<i>varname</i>) del (<i>container</i> , <i>key</i>)	removes a variable from the stack, resp. the entry identified by <i>key</i> from a container returns a Boolean indicating success
concat (<i>arg1</i> , <i>arg2</i> , ...)	concatenates the given arguments if all types match and returns a container
len (<i>arg</i>)	returns the length of a container
dict_keys (<i>d</i>)	returns a list of keys used in the <i>dict</i> <i>d</i>
whoami ()	returns the user's public key identifier in hex
read (<i>key</i>) read (<i>table_name</i> , <i>key</i>) read (<i>table_name</i> , <i>revision</i> , <i>key</i>)	returns the data value referenced by <i>key</i> of the current or remote database entry
write (<i>key</i> , <i>value</i>)	writes a value in the table of the current entry
write_code (<i>function_name</i> , <i>code</i>)	<i>not implemented</i> ; writes code in the contract
write_acl (<i>to be defined</i>)	<i>not implemented</i> ; updates the ACL
write_accessors (<i>to be defined</i>)	<i>not implemented</i> ; updates the accessors list

Table 3.3: List of currently available built-ins.

3.4 RESULT

SCALD investigates the possibilities and properties of a language for Smart Contracts in database environments. The Turing incomplete language and corresponding design decisions enable the secure execution of Smart Contract Code without a dedicated virtualization layer. Despite the limitations that Turing's incompleteness brings with it, SCALD can easily be extended with new features in the form of built-in functions. This should allow the implementation of all functions important for Smart Contracts. Furthermore, the Syntax of SCALD aims to result in easy to understand and unambiguous source code, which minimizes the possibilities to obfuscate malicious functionality.

Since all database interactions are provided by a dedicated interface, rights management is implemented here. ACL compliance checks are already functional and additional features like signature checking could be realized as well. Providing basic cryptographic functionality in SCALD would probably lead to interesting consequences and is worth exploring.

The security of the executing computers is directly related to the security of the SCALD interpreter. The developed implementation⁸ therefore contains more than 580 tests for all language features and is well documented. Even though the language is still in its early stages, it already contains the most important building blocks to develop Smart Contracts. In conclusion, SCALD is a good starting point for further research in the field of Smart Contracts on databases and thus fulfills the desired goal.

Further improvements of SCALD's syntax and interpreter should also be covered by automated tests to prevent errors and more important malicious code injections. Another promising topic for further research would be the development of a higher level Smart Contract language on top of SCALD and ETHVAM. Such research could determine, for instance, if precise read control is possible by automatically generating multiple ETHVAM entries and Smart Contracts for each process definition. A resulting metalanguage that allows code and ACL generation for SCALD and ETHVAM would further improve the usability and relevance for real world applications.

⁸The source code is published at

<https://emcl-gitlab.iwr.uni-heidelberg.de/olaf.pichler/masterthesis/>.

4 APPLICATION EXAMPLES

This chapter provides a proof of concept and two increasingly complex examples of the use of ETHVAM. For reasons of legibility, the level of detail in the description will decrease as the complexity of the example increases.

4.1 PROOF OF CONCEPT

A minimal proof of concept was performed. The example consists of a security context with one validator, one client and one database entry.

```
entry_data = dict()
entry_data["creator"] = node_sk.pub_key.for_json()
entry_data["accessors"] = objects.Accessors([node_sk.pub_key,
                                             validator_pub_key] \
                                             ).for_json()

entry_data["data"] = {"data_point": 0}
entry_data["code"] = '''increment()
{
    var = read("data_point");
    return write("data_point", var+1);
}'''
entry_data["acl"] = objects.ACL([objects.ACL_function_entry("increment",
    [objects.ACL_base_entry(
        node_sk.pub_key,
        str(arrow.now().replace(days=+10)))]),
    [objects.ACL_data_entry("data_point",
    [objects.ACL_base_entry(
        node_sk.pub_key,
        str(arrow.now().replace(days=+10)))])] \
    ).for_json()
entry_data["history"] = objects.History(node_table_name,
-1, '', []).for_json()
entry_data["timestamp"] = str(arrow.now())
```

Listing 4.1: Excerpt of the entry creation showing the setup of the entries data section.

4 Application Examples

The client is allowed to create new entries and adds a minimal Smart Contract with the sole purpose of incrementing a counter. In the above listing, the setup of the initial entry is displayed. The entry is only readable by the author and the validator who will approve the entry. The ACLs allow only the client to update the entry in a ten days period beginning with the entry's creation.

The validator setup in general is very easy. It first loads all the configurations from an encrypted file that contains its private key, database credentials and the table name of the clients list of its security context. Afterwards, it simply enters the validation loop.

```
validator = Validator()
validator.load_config(private_key_path_validator, private_key_password)

while True:
    try:
        validator.validate_proposals()
    except ValidationError as err:
        report_validation_error(err)
```

Listing 4.2: Validator setup.

The client setup may be more complex depending on the task. In this case, it is especially simple because the client does not have to interact with other clients.

```
node = Node()
node.load_config(private_key_path_node, private_key_password)

enc_row = node.db_Worldstate_connection.getLastRowOfTable(node_table_name)
revision_number = enc_row.rev
node.run_contract(node_table_name, "increment", [])

while True:
    # test if proposed entry is already approved
    enc_row = node.db_Worldstate_connection.getLastRowOfTable(node_table_name)
    if enc_row.rev == revision_number:
        sleep(2)
        continue
    else:
        revision_number = enc_row.rev
        node.run_contract(node_table_name, "increment", [])
```

Listing 4.3: Client setup.

In the responsible security context, the *data_point* will now be incremented infinitely by the client.

4.2 SIMPLE EXAMPLE

To provide an example that uses more of ETHVAM's and SCALD's features, one can assume a game of Go played by two clients. They will alternate in putting a black or white stone on the board. Furthermore, a commentator will report and analyze the game for a broader audience. The players are only supposed to take a turn one after the other in order to prevent cheating. They will be called Alice and Bob and the commentator will go by the name Carol. The game's data as well as the contract is stored in an ETHVAM database table named *gogame*.

The data section of the implementation of such a contract could look like this:

```
last_turn = 'white'
go_board = ...[]
```

The code for the contract would be:

```
play(xpos, ypos, color){
  /* This function checks the rules and performs writes to "go_board" */
}
whites_turn(xpos, ypos){
  if(read(last_turn) == "black"){
    write("last_turn", "white");
    return play(xpos, ypos, "white");
  }
  return False;
}
blacks_turn(xpos, ypos){
  if(read(last_turn) == "white"){
    write("last_turn", "black");
    return play(xpos, ypos, "black");
  }
  return False;
}
```

entry function ACL

- function: `play`
remains empty
- function: `whites_turn`
Alice's public key
- function: `blacks_turn`
Bob's public key

data ACL

- key: `last_turn`
Alice's public key
Bob's public key
- function: `go_board`
Alice's public key
Bob's public key

4 Application Examples

The `play` function contains all the game logic and returns `True` if a valid move was played. To ensure that the players turns are alternating, separate turn functions for each player are defined. It has to be guaranteed that both players can use the `play` function only if the check for the play order was performed first. This is ensured by the entry function ACL while the data ACL allows both players to update the game state.

Finally, the read access to the data will be discussed. At that point, not only Alice and Bob must be considered, but Carol also needs access to the game's data to report about it. The access rights to the `gogame` table are cryptographically controlled by the ETHVAM system. All relevant data is encrypted, so for this example to be complete Alice, Bob and Carol need to be able to decrypt the `gogame` table.

The beginning of the ETHVAM table entries would contain this:

revision		key encrypted for <i>Validator</i>	
–	encrypted contract data	key encrypted for <i>Alice</i>	...
number		key encrypted for <i>Bob</i>	
		key encrypted for <i>Carol</i>	
		keyslot padding ...	

Now, the contract is fully defined and Alice and Bob can start playing. The encryption ensures that only Alice, Bob and Carol can access the games data so Carol can report exclusively¹. The ACLs ensure only Alice and Bob can change the game's state and enforce safety measures so that cheating becomes impossible.

¹The validator also reads the data in order to verify correctness.

4.3 ADVANCED EXAMPLE

A more practical example will subsequently be discussed assuming that a company wants to coordinate its deliveries with ETHVAM.

The company receiving goods, henceforth called *Omega Company* or Ω , creates an entry with all possible delivery terms. All suppliers can register timeslots in this entry. Subsequently, the suppliers offer Smart Contracts which allow Ω to buy goods. An order creates a new entry in the Worldstate database which ensures that only the contracting parties have access to it. Additionally, a unique identifier, the table name, is created. Only the identifier is added to the Smart Contract regarding the offer. It indicates to the concerned supplier, going by *Kappa* or κ , that a valid order was placed. κ can now book a timeslot with the order identifier. Upon acceptance of the delivery, the supplier receives a signed time stamp from Ω as proof of delivery. These signed timestamp is used by κ to create a payment request in the orders table. Finally Ω can mark the order as payed which finalizes the order.

In figure 4.1, a draft of the necessary Worldstate entries is shown. The ACLs are to big to visualize them effectively. Therefore, the functions were marked in color. Blue writing means that this function can only be executed by Ω and red writing means that only κ can use this function.

To discuss the setup in more detail, it is assumed that the “product offer entry” (POE) as well as the “delivery timeslots entry” (DTE) are already created. The POE is maintained by κ and provides at least an *add_order* clause that takes a Worldstate table name as a parameter which references the actual order. The DTE was created by Ω and specifies the times at which deliveries are possible. Ω can add more delivery periods at any time with *create_timeslot*. Suppliers can plan ordered deliveries with *claim_timeslot* and prevent unnecessary waiting times due to congestion at the receiving area.

When Ω plans to order goods from κ , it first looks at the POE to get the current product list and then reviews the terms of the Smart Contracts *add_order* function, which can be rather complex. Next, Ω creates an “order entry” (OE) that specifies the amount of goods. This entry also needs to satisfy the conditions of κ , which are defined in the POE. For this example, κ gives a guarantee to deliver before a predetermined date. After the OE becomes Worldstate, Ω informs κ about the order by invoking

Figure 4.1: Simplified visualization of the Worldstate database entries.

add_order with the table name of the newly created OE. The *add_order* function will check if the order is valid. This involves testing the accessor list, the data, the ACL and the Smart Contract's code of the OE. When κ prepares the delivery they pick a timeslot from the DTE and execute *claim_timeslot* with the desired timeslot and the table name of the OE. This function checks if the timeslot is still free as well as if the order was created by Ω and afterwards updates the timeslot table.

At the delivery date, *Kappa's* product arrives at Ω and is exchanged for a delivery confirmation, in form of a signed timestamp. In combination with a mobile client, κ can mark the order as delivered on the spot. Finally, Ω will pay for the delivery and complete the order process by appending the transaction identifier to the OE with *mark_order_payed*.

4.4 FURTHER USE CASES AND PROSPECTS

The described examples cover only a sliver of ETHVAM's capabilities and the possibilities of this system are manifold. Different competing companies, could for instance, optimize their supply chains and capacity utilization without having to make sensitive information accessible to competitors.

Moreover, it would also be conceivable to network medical devices in a clinic. Each device would become an ETHVAM client participating in the creation of encrypted patient files. The resulting data would be readable only by authorized persons and accessible in coded patient files for the treating physician within short times. In this case the, clinic would host their own SC to enforce confidentiality of the data.

Another possible use case is the identification and traceability of goods. In larger production chains or in the food industries, a faulty component could be traced back to the responsible producer and the affected batch identified. With such information, all affected purchasers could be informed. Furthermore, the information about ingredients would not be accessible to competitors but only to the responsible entity. This could be an agency, the quality management bureau or any other supervising entity.

Furthermore, the proof of concept shows that ETHVAM in combination with SCALD form a working system. The presented examples provide an insight to the capabilities of this system although it was not possible to implement and test these in practice due to the time constraints of this project.

In conclusion, further studies are required to get an understanding of the performance and throughput properties of ETHVAM and SCALD. Especially the scaling effects on the underlying CockroachDB are interesting. Future research in that direction will require a larger test setup with multiple security contexts that incorporate different example use cases at the same time. Hence, a refined statement on the differences and similarities between ETHVAM's and the Blockchain approach for Smart Contracts could be made.

5 CONCLUSION

The feasibility of a Smart Contract system on the basis of distributed databases was explored in this thesis as an alternative to the Blockchain framework.

Additionally, the research on the *Encrypted Transaction-History Validation and Authentication Model* revealed a set of interesting findings. To begin with, it was proven that Smart Contracts based on distributed databases are possible.

Moreover, the introduction of trusted third parties, the validators, removed the necessity for distributed controlling, which is the origin of most of the problems of Blockchains. The validators perform all the control duties and ensure that only valid entries contribute to the Worldstate. In addition to the validators, the participants can also still audit all entries and the history concerning them. In theory, this approach scales without limits and any throughput issues can be solved by adding database or validator nodes to the system. Furthermore, the distributed database allows to create entries of any size and does not rely on a fixed number of transactions that are accumulated to a block. This improves ETHVAM's latency in comparison to a Blockchain system. As a consequence of the task separation, it is possible to revert added Worldstate entries in the exceptional cases of erroneous or malicious entries. Even though this diminishes the security a bit, no single instance of ETHVAM can revert entries on its own. Database administrators can delete entries only on demand and have no possibility to read contents of any entry. On the other hand, validators and clients can read entries related to them, but cannot delete them.

Although the task separation enhances the security of ETHVAM in respect to the identified problems of Blockchains, it causes other security issues instead. The security evaluation revealed that a successful attack on one of the validators compromises its complete security context and is hard to detect. Blockchain systems, on the other hand, have no nodes with privileged rights as long as no single participant operates more than 50% of the mining capacity. However, for smaller Blockchain networks and private

5 Conclusion

Blockchains, this can become a problem because an attacker can easily buy enough computing power to surpass 50% of their mining capacity. Additionally, miners must have a minimum monetary incentive that is sufficient to build up competitive pressure leading to mutual control. ETHVAM, in contrast, is not designed to implement a digital currency. Thus, compliance with the rules is enforced by dedicated entities without competitive interests. Further research is required to determine, whether ETHVAM's weaknesses can be eliminated or mitigated, for instance by implementing a decision quorum of several validators.

Therefore, to showcase the Smart Contract capability of ETHVAM, the *Smart Contract Application Language for Databases*, was developed to formulate them in an accessible way. SCALD is designed Turing incomplete for simplicity and security reasons. This allows the execution of Smart Contracts in a not hardened or virtualized environment. SCALD is independent of the used database, because it uses an interface to communicate with ETHVAM as well as the distributed databases. This interface also implements the ACL features of ETHVAM, which allows authors of Smart Contracts to specify restrictions for function execution and data modification. As another advantage, this feature allows automated tests to ensure that all accessors can actually read the entry.

Furthermore, the functionality of SCALD is currently limited but easily expandable by built in functions due to the parser choice and the Python based interpreter. It might even be possible to develop a metalanguage on top of SCALD that allows authors to specify read permissions alike write permissions in an ACL. Therefore, the necessary SCALD code as well as the needed database entries can then be generated automatically by the metalanguage interpreter. Thus, the database interaction and other language capabilities were tested in application and a proof of concept was realized. On this basis, further example use cases were designed that could be realized with SCALD's current development state.

Finally, ETHVAM and SCALD form an evaluated proof of concept system that has the potential to become a solution for economic use cases. This system overcomes most of the Blockchain's problems with the trade-off of granting a controlling instance access to the Smart Contracts and their data. In future, performance evaluations and big scale experiments will show if the described system is feasible for real world applications. Also, a more detailed security analysis involving a penetration test to detect additional security issues is equally important. In conclusion, ETHVAM and SCALD proved to be a promising basis for further scientific experiments in the field of Blockchain and Smart Contracts research.

APPENDIX

SCALD'S GRAMMAR

filename: scald.lark

root : function+

function : function_name "(" param_list ")" function_body

param_list : (param ("," param)*)?

function_body : "{" statement+ "}"

function_name : ID

?param : ID

statement : "return" expression ";" → return_statement
| if_block elif_block* [else_block] → if_statement
| "for" "(" for_arguments ")" statement_list → for_statement
| expression ";" → eval_statement

if_block : "if" "(" condition ")" statement_list

elif_block: "elif" "(" condition ")" statement_list

else_block: "else" statement_list

condition : expression

statement_list : "{" statement+ "}"

for_arguments : ID "," expression ("," expression)~0..2

// expressions need to be ordered by precedence

// expression_0 has the least precedence

expression : expression_0

Appendix

```
?expression_0 : expression_1
               | ID "=" expression_0 -> assignment
               | ID "[" expression_0 DUMMY expression_0 -> field_assignment
// This is a workaround to make the lalr parser recognize ] = as a token
DUMMY.50 : /]\s*\=(?!=)/

?expression_1 : expression_2
               | expression_1 "||" expression_2 -> or

?expression_2 : expression_3
               | expression_2 "&&" expression_3 -> and

?expression_3 : expression_4
               | expression_3 "==" expression_4 -> equals
               | expression_3 "!=" expression_4 -> nequals

?expression_4 : expression_5
               | expression_4 "<" expression_5 -> smaller
               | expression_4 ">" expression_5 -> bigger
               | expression_4 "<=" expression_5 -> smallereq
               | expression_4 ">=" expression_5 -> biggereq

?expression_5 : expression_6
               | expression_5 "+" expression_6 -> add
               | expression_5 "-" expression_6 -> subtract

?expression_6 : expression_7
               | expression_6 "*" expression_7 -> multiply
               | expression_6 "/" expression_7 -> divide
               | expression_6 "%" expression_7 -> modulo

?expression_7 : expression_8
               | "-" expression_7 -> neg
               | "!" expression_7 -> not

?expression_8 : expression_9
               | "[" expression_list "]" -> list_definition
               | "[" dict_entry_list "]" -> dict_definition
               | "(" expression ")"

?expression_9 : INT
               | FLT
               | STR
               | BOOL
               | ID -> access
               | ID "[" expression "]" -> field_access
               | function_name "(" expression_list ")" -> function_call
               | predefined_function
               | predefined_const
               | cast_function
               | database_function
```

```

expression_list : (expression ("," expression)*)?
dict_entry_list : dict_entry ("," dict_entry)* | ":"
dict_entry: expression ":" expression

?cast_function : "int" "(" expression ")" -> int_cast
                | "float" "(" expression ")" -> flt_cast
                | "bool" "(" expression ")" -> bool_cast
                | "str" "(" expression ")" -> str_cast

?predefined_function : "fact" "(" expression ")" -> fact
                      | "pow" "(" expression "," expression ")" -> pow
                      | "sqrt" "(" expression ")" -> sqrt
                      | "sqrt" "(" expression "," expression ")" -> sqrt2
                      | "exp" "(" expression ")" -> exp
                      | "log" "(" expression ")" -> log
                      | "log10" "(" expression ")" -> log10
                      | "log2" "(" expression ")" -> log2
                      | "sin" "(" expression ")" -> sin
                      | "cos" "(" expression ")" -> cos
                      | "tan" "(" expression ")" -> tan
                      | "arcsin" "(" expression ")" -> arcsin
                      | "arccos" "(" expression ")" -> arccos
                      | "arctan" "(" expression ")" -> arctan
                      | "arctan" "(" expression "," expression ")" ->
                        ↪ arctan2
                      | "sinh" "(" expression ")" -> sinh
                      | "cosh" "(" expression ")" -> cosh
                      | "tanh" "(" expression ")" -> tanh
                      | "arcsinh" "(" expression ")" -> arcsinh
                      | "arccosh" "(" expression ")" -> arccosh
                      | "arctanh" "(" expression ")" -> arctanh
                      | "type" "(" expression ")" -> type
                      | "print" "(" expression_list ")" -> print
                      | "concat" "(" expression_list ")" -> concat
                      | "dict_keys" "(" expression ")" -> dict_keys
                      | "len" "(" expression ")" -> len
                      | "del" "(" expression ")" -> del
                      | "del" "(" expression "," expression ")" -> del_entry

// 1) read a data value from current entry identified by valuname
// 2) read a data value from the DB identified by tablename, revision and
    ↪ valuname
// 3) write data into local key value store
?database_function : "read" "(" expression ")" -> db_read_local
                   | "read" "(" expression "," expression "," expression ")"
                     ↪ " -> db_read_global
                   | "write" "(" expression "," expression ")" ->
                     ↪ db_write_data
                   // TODO: | "write_code" "(" ... ")" -> db_write_code
                   // TODO: | "write_acl" "(" ... ")" -> db_write_acl
                   // TODO: | "write_accessors" "(" ... ")" -> db_write_acl

```

Appendix

```
.....
?predefined_const : PI

FLT : /\d+\.\d*/
INT : /\d+/
ID : /[A-Za-z_][\w_]*/
STR : /".*?(?!\\)(\\\\)*?"/is
BOOL.9 : /(True|False)/
PI.10: "PI"

COMMENT : /\/*(.\n)*?\*\\/
%ignore COMMENT

%import common.WS
%ignore WS
```


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Heidelberg, 30th August, 2019

Olaf Pichler

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